

Mutual Interfitting Property of the Honeycomb Rhombus and the Double-Fibonacci Rhombus and Their Polyhedron Construction--Figure

Fig1_Honeycomb_DoubleFib.png

Fig. 1: Basic parameter comparison between the honeycomb rhombus (left) and the double-Fibonacci rhombus (right)

Fig2_BII_FourVariants.png

Fig. 2 : BII- type dodecahedron family (from left to right: standard type, skewed type, spin- 1/2 type (same side as completely asymmetric type), completely asymmetric type)

Fig3_Spin12_Front_Back.png

Fig. 3: Spin- 1/2 type (front view, back view)

Fig4_Mixed_Hexa_Dodeca.png

Fig. 4 Symmetric mixed hexahedron (blue: double- Fibonacci rhombus) and symmetric mixed dodecahedron (blue: double- Fibonacci rhombus)

Fig5_90Degree_Example.png

